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IN VITRO ANTIOXIDANT POTENCY STUDIES OF HYDRO ALCOHOLIC LEAF EXTRACT OF CASSIA UNIFLORA

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ABSTRACT

To study the antioxidant potency of hydro alcoholic extract of Cassia uniflora. Hydro alcoholic leaf extracts of the plants was studied for its Free radical scavenging activity against DPPH, ABST and Superoxide ion. Hydro alcoholic crude extracts of leaves of Cassia uniflora at concentrations of 10, 25, and 50µg/ml were studied against DPPH, ABST and Superoxide ion to know their antioxidant potential. Cassia uniflora leaf hydro alcoholic extract possessed an IC50 value 26.32 µg/ml in DPPH radical scavenging assay on compare to standard Vitamin C (3.59µg/ml), in ABST radical scavenging assay 8.76 µg/ml and standard vitamin C (2.32 µg/ml) and in Super oxide ion scavenging recorded as 45.84 µg/ml and for standard gallic acid was found to 0.61 µg/ml. The crude extracts showing better activity against DPPH ABST and Superoxide ion. Hence, can be recommended for potential usage as an antioxidant agent in pharmaceutical and nutraceutical industries.

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INTRODUCTION

Plants are the relevance asset of medications of traditional system of pharmaceutical. Plants have been utilized as conventional therapeutic agent for various human ailments for a great many a long time. The many number of medicinal plants are used in the cellular and metabolic disease treatment such as diabetes, obesity and cancer etc. There are some speculations that the generation of free radicals inside the body in some physiological conditions is resulted in the cellular changes and development of cancer etc. and this could be neutralized by the antioxidants from different medicinal plants. Several studies have shown that plant derived antioxidant nutraceuticals scavenge free radicals and modulate oxidative stress-related degenerative effects [1, 2]. Free radicals have been implicated in many diseases such as cancer, atherosclerosis, diabetes, neurodegenerative disorders and aging [3, 4].

Lipid autooxidation is a radical procedure engaged with a chain response including induction, proliferation and termination steps. Amid the induction time, alkyl and peroxy radicals are generated. These exceedingly reactive chemical species deliver hydroperoxides (ROOH) at the propagation stage. Termination is the clubbing of two radicals together to generate more stable products. The entire process is responsible for organoleptic and nutritional changes because of the development of offflavour volatile compounds from breakdown of ROOH and the vanishing of essential fatty acids. Besides, radicals generated are associated with the ageing of tissues and pathologies, like cancer or cardiovascular diseases [5]. Therefore, it is important to protect diet lipids and human tissues against free radicals by endogenous and exogenous cell antioxidants from a natural or synthetic origin.

Antioxidants are substances that hinder or defer the oxidation of other compounds by inhibiting the induction or propagation of oxidizing chain responses. There are two essential classifications of antioxidant agents, to be specific, synthetic and natural. Generally, synthetic antioxidants are compounds with phenolic structures of different degrees of alkyl substitution, while natural oxidation preventing agents can be phenolic compounds (tocopherols, flavonoids, and phenolic acids), nitrogenous substances (alkaloids, chlorophyll subsidiaries, amino acids, and amines), or carotenoids and in addition ascorbic acids [6, 7, 8]. Synthetic oxidation prevention agents, for example, butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) and butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) have been utilized as antioxidant since the beginning of this century. Limitations on the use of these compounds, because of their cancer-causing nature [9; 10]. Thus, the interest in natural antioxidants has increased considerably [11].

Cassia uniflora (C. uniflora) (Mill.) is an herb having a place with family Caesalpiniaceae [12]. The young leaves of the plant eaten as vegetables. The dried stems can be utilized as fuel. A poultice of the leaves is used for wound healing and the extract is accounted for treatment of particular sorts of skin inflammation. The roots are utilized to combat dropsy. The C. uniflora has not been assessed for its chemical composition but rather it was reported for to contain protein, polyphenols and alpha galactosidase [13]. Polyphenols are one of the phytoconstituents of this plant and in various literature it was explain polyphenols having antioxidant properties hence we decided to measure the free radical scavenging potency of leaf of this plant.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material and preparation of extracts

Stem, fruit and leaves of *Cassia uniflora* were collected from Rajahmandri, East Godavari district. They were collected in the month of January 2011. They were authenticated by Dr. K. N. Reddy, Dept. of taxonomy, Laila impex R&D Centre, Vijayawada. The plant materials were deposited in raw drug museum, Laila impex, R&D centre. The voucher no. of leaf material was 3317.

The plant material was air dried completely under shade to eliminate moisture content. It was powdered mechanically to coarse or fine powder.

Phytochemical screening:

The powdered leaves of *Cassia uniflora* were extracted with a mixture of water and alcohol (3:7) and resultant extract was subjected for phytochemical analysis to identify different phytoconstituents as per standard procedures. [14, 15]

Anti oxidant activity

DPPH radical scavenging assay

DPPH radical scavenging potency was carried out by the standard reported method [16]; the reaction mixture containing 1 mL of DPPH solution (0.1 mmol/L, in 95% ethanol v/v) with various concentration of the extract was shaken and incubated for 20 min at room temperature and the absorbance was measured at 517 nm against a blank. The radical scavenging action was measured as a decreasing in the absorbance of DPPH and figured utilizing the formula:

$$\text{DPPH scavenging activity (\%)} = (A_0 - A_1) / A_0 \times 100$$

Where A_0 is the absorbance of the control and A_1 is the absorbance of the sample.

ABTS radical scavenging activity

An ABTS radical-scavenging property of the extract was assayed according to Re et al [17]. The ABTS⁺ cation radical was formed by the reaction between 5 ml of 14 mM ABTS solution and 5 ml of 4.9 mM potassium persulfate (K₂S₂O₈) solution, keep aside in dark at room temperature for 16 h. Before use, this solution was diluted with ethanol to get an absorbance of 0.700 ± 0.020 at 734 nm. The plant extract at different concentration with 1ml of ABTS solution was homogenized and its absorbance was read at 734 nm. Ethanol was taken as blank in each test, and all estimations were done after atleast 6 min. in the similar way, the reaction mixture of standard was recorded by mixing 950 µl of ABTS⁺ solution and 50 µl of BHT. With respect to the antiradical activity, ABTS scavenging capacity was expressed as IC₅₀ (µg/ml). The inhibition level of ABTS radical was ascertained using the equation:

$$\text{ABTS scavenging activity (\%)} = (A_0 - A_1) / A_0 \times 100$$

Where A₀ is the absorbance of the control, and A₁ is the absorbance of the sample.

Assay for Superoxide ion Scavenging Activity

The assay for superoxide ion scavenging activity was done as per standard procedure Beuchamp C et al., 1997 [18]. The reaction mixture contained 50mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.6), 20 µg riboflavin, 12mM EDTA and 0.1 mg/ml of NBT (nitro blue tetrazolium), all added in chronological sequence. Reaction was started by illuminating the reaction mixture containing different concentration of sample extract for 90 sec and then measuring the absorbance at 590nm. Gallic acid was taken as the positive standard.

$$\% \text{ of inhibition} = \text{Control absorbance} - \text{Test absorbance} / \text{Control absorbance} \times 100$$

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Phytochemical Screening

The phytochemical screening of hydro alcoholic extracts from leaves confirmed the existence of several families of secondary metabolites of biological and pharmacological interest such as alkaloids, quinones, coumarins, resins. Triterpenoids, Saponin, carbohydrates, phenols, tannins, flavonoids.

Antioxidant activity assay

Polyphenols are one of the large and diverse class of compounds, a significant number of which occurs naturally in a wide variety of nourishment and plants. The flavonoids are the largest and best examined compound among polyphenols. A number of plant polyphenols is either being effectively developed or currently sold as dietary supplements or potential herbal derived medicine. Despite the fact that these compounds play an obscure role in nourishment, a large number of them have properties including antioxidant, anti-mutagenic, anti-cancer-causing and anti-inflammatory impacts that may conceivably be useful in preventing disease and protecting the stability of genome [19]. Free radical scavenging properties is a measure of the effectiveness of the antioxidant(s) present as an unadulterated compound or a mixture [20]. The rate of scavenging and IC₅₀ esteems were computed for all models.

DPPH radical scavenging assay

The reactivity of hydro alcoholic extract of Cassia uniflora leaves was examined with DPPH, a stable free radical. As DPPH gains one electron in the presence of a free radical scrounger, the absorption diminishes and the subsequent discolouration is stoichiometrically related with the quantity of electrons picked up [21]. Cassia uniflora leaf hydro alcoholic extract possessed an IC₅₀ value 26.32 µg/ml and standard vitamin C was 3.59µg/ml. The result is given in table No. 1. and figure No. 1.

Table 1: DPPH radical scavenging activity of Cassia uniflora.

Test	Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition	IC ₅₀ (µg/ml)
CULH	10	23.345±0.029	26.32
	25	50.54±0.028	
	50	85.34±0.024	
Vitamin-C	1	18.32±0.034	3.59
	2.5	41.126±0.027	
	5	64.24±0.029	

Result is expressed as Mean ± SEM (n=3).

Fig 1: DPPH radical scavenging activity of *Cassia uniflora*.

ABTS radical scavenging activity

The ABTS⁺ radical scavenging assay, which utilizes a particular absorbance (734 nm) at a wavelength far-off from the visible region and requires a short reaction time, can be utilized as an index that emulates the antioxidant action of the test samples [22].

The hydro alcoholic leaves extract of *Cassia uniflora* was observed to be successful in scavenging radicals and the rise was concentration subordinate. The inhibition of the concentrate was 8.76 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and standard vitamin C was observed to be 2.32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. This demonstrates *C. uniflora* leaf extract introduces a good capacity to scavenging the ABTS radical. The results are shown in tableNo.2 and figure No. 2.

Table 2: ABTS radical scavenging activity of *Cassia uniflora*.

Test compound	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Inhibition $\pm$ SEM	IC ₅₀
CULH	2.5	27.25 $\pm$ 0.030	8.76
	5	38.273 $\pm$ 0.044	
	10	53.833 $\pm$ 0.038	
Vitamin C	1	39.296 $\pm$ 0.012	2.32
	2.5	51.563 $\pm$ 0.070	
	5	68.943 $\pm$ 0.029	

Result is expressed as Mean $\pm$ SEM (n=3)

Fig. 2: ABTS radical scavenging activity of *Cassia uniflora*.

Superoxide ion Scavenging Assay

In the phenazine methosulphate/Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide-nitroblue tetrazolium (PMS/NADH-NBT) system, superoxide anion is produced by a nonenzymatic reaction of phenazine methosulphate in the presence of NADH and molecular oxygen [23, 24].

NBT reduces by Superoxide anion into formazan at pH 7.8 at room temperature and formazan formation is followed by spectrophotometry at 560 nm. The diminishing of absorbance at 560 nm with antioxidant in this way demonstrates the utilization of superoxide anion in the reaction mixture.

The superoxide anion radical-scavenging action of the extract might be because of the presence of phenolic phytochemicals. The IC₅₀ was recorded 45.84 µg/ml for *Cassia uniflora* leaves hydro alcoholic extract and for standard gallic acid was found to 0.61 µg/ml. The increase in action is because of increase in number of phenolic hydroxyl group in the molecule. The results are shown in table No.3 and figure No. 3.

Table 3: Superoxide radical scavenging activity of *Cassia uniflora*.

Test compound	Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition ± SEM	IC ₅₀ (µg/ml)
CUFW	10	24.246±0.023	45.84
	25	2.10±0.055	
	50	53.943±0.026	
Gallic acid	0.25	20.543±0.049	0.61
	0.5	38.93±0.030	
	0.75	55.85±0.040	

Result is expressed as Mean ± SEM (n=3).

Fig. 3: Superoxide radical scavenging activity of *Cassia uniflora*.

CONCLUSION

In the previous couple of years, enthusiasm for the finding of new natural antioxidant has increased because reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation and oxidative stress is connected to numerous diseases. The use of synthetic antioxidants prompts issues of toxicity. Free radical is a particle with an unpaired electron and is associated with bacterial and parasitic infection, lung damage, inflammation, reperfusion damage, cardiovascular disorder, atherosclerosis, aging and neoplastic diseases [25]. They are additionally involved with immune system disorders like rheumatoid joint inflammation etc [26, 27]. Along these lines, look into for the determination of the natural antioxidant source is important.

In this investigation, we conclude that hydro alcoholic leaves extract of *Cassia uniflora* has better antioxidant property and could be credited to the presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponin glycosides and phenolic phytoconstituents. The aftereffects of this investigation demonstrate that hydro alcoholic leaves extract of *Cassia uniflora* and its constituents can be useful as an effortlessly open wellspring of natural antioxidant and as a conceivable supplement or in pharmaceutical industry. Further study is required for the mechanism of action of its free radical scavenging activity and for future use.

List of abbreviation

DPPH : 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl
 ABST : 2-2'-Azino-di-[3-ethylbenzthiazoline sulfonate]
 CULH : *Cassia uniflora* leaf hydro alcoholic extract, µg/ml

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